

A STUDY OF CHINESE TOURISTS' PERCEPTION OF GASTRONOMIC TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF “ONE BELT, ONE ROAD”.

A WEB CONTENT ANALYSIS BASED ON DIANPING.COM

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Abstract. *Based on the background of “One Belt, One Road”, this study takes the online reviews of Chinese tourists on Uzbekistan's gastronomic tourism on Dianping.com as the data source, and applies the text content analysis method to explore the Chinese tourists' Gastronomic Tourism in Uzbekistan through high-frequency word analysis, semantic network analysis and sentiment analysis. It was found that Chinese tourists' perceptions of Uzbekistan's gastronomic tourism focused on five aspects: gastronomic products, gastronomic services, gastronomic environment, tourist destinations and tourists' perceptions. Semantic network analysis shows that tourists' evaluations of gastronomic tourism present a “core - edge” hierarchical structure, with restaurants as the central node in the core layer, covering keywords such as food variety and gastronomic quality; the edge layer involves vocabulary related to tourism infrastructure and landmarks. Sentiment analysis shows that tourists' positive sentiments are dominant (86.96%), and negative sentiments mainly stem from the discomfort of dietary differences and poor service. Based on the results of the study, suggestions are made to create specialties, optimize the restaurant experience, improve the supporting services of gastronomic tourism and expand the promotion strategy, aiming to help Uzbekistan to improve the quality of gastronomic tourism products and services, promote the development of local tourism, and at the same time, provide a new perspective for the study of cross-cultural gastronomic tourism in the countries along the “One Belt, One Road” and an empirical basis. It also provides new perspectives and empirical evidence for the study of intercultural gastronomic tourism in countries along the “Belt and Road”.*

Key words: *Uzbekistan, Gastronomic Tourism, Chinese Tourists, Perception Analysis, the content analysis.*

Аннотация: *На фоне инициативы «Один пояс, один путь» данное исследование использует онлайн-отзывы китайских туристов о гастрономическом туризме Узбекистана на платформе Dianping.com в качестве источника данных. Применяя метод текстового контент-анализа, включая анализ высокочастотных слов, сетевой семантический анализ и сентимент-анализ, исследование изучает восприятие, эмоциональные оценки и удовлетворенность китайских туристов гастрономическим туризмом Узбекистана. Результаты показывают, что восприятие туристов сосредоточено на пяти аспектах: гастрономические продукты (например, мясные блюда, плов, баранина), услуги в сфере питания, ресторанный среда, туристические направления и восприятие туристов. Семантический сетевой анализ выявил иерархическую структуру «ядро-периферия», где ядро (ресторан) связано с ключевыми словами, такими как разнообразие блюд и качество еды, а периферия включает термины,*

связанные с туристической инфраструктурой и достопримечательностями. Сентимент-анализ показал преобладание позитивных оценок (86,96%), обусловленных уникальными вкусами и культурным погружением, тогда как негативные эмоции (10,14%) связаны с дискомфортом из-за различий в питании и неудовлетворительным обслуживанием. На основе результатов предложены рекомендации: создание уникальных блюд, оптимизация ресторанного опыта, улучшение инфраструктуры гастротуризма и расширение маркетинговых стратегий. Эти меры направлены на помощь Узбекистану в повышении качества гастрономического туризма, развитии местной индустрии и предоставлении новых перспектив для межкультурных исследований в странах «Пояса и пути».

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан; гастрономический туризм; китайские туристы; анализ восприятия; контент-анализ.

Annotatsiya. “Bir Kamar, Bir Yo’l” tashabbusi kontekstida bu tadqiqot Xitoy sayyohlarining O‘zbekiston gastronomik turizmi haqidagi onlayn sharhlarini Dianping.com platformasidan ma’lumot manbai sifatida foydalanadi. Matn kontentini tahlil qilish usuli (yuqori chastotali so‘zlar tahlili, semantik tarmoq tahlili va hissiyotlar tahlili) orqali Xitoy sayyohlarining O‘zbekiston gastronomik turizmi haqidagi idrok, hissiy ifodalari va qoniqish darajasi o‘rganildi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko‘rsatdiki, sayyohlarning idroki besh aspektga qaratilgan: gastronomik mahsulotlar (masalan, grill go’sht, osh, qo‘y go’shti), ovqatlanish xizmatlari, restoran muhiti, sayyohlik manzillari va sayyohlarning idroki. Semantik tarmoq tahlili “yadro-periferiya” ierarxik tuzilishini ko‘rsatadi, bunda yadro qismida “restoran” markaziy tugun bo‘lib, ovqat turlari va sifatini aks ettiruvchi kalit so‘zlar joylashgan; periferiya esa turizm infratuzilmasi va diqqatga sazovor joylar bilan bog‘liq so‘zlarni o‘z ichiga oladi. Hissiyotlar tahlili asosan ijobiy baholarni (86.96%) ko‘rsatadi, bu esa mahalliy ta’mlar va madaniy tajriba bilan bog‘liq. Salbiy baholar (10.14%) ovqatlanish farqlari va xizmat sifatsizligi sababli yuzaga keladi. Tadqiqot natijalariga asosan, O‘zbekistonga gastronomik turizm mahsulotlari sifatini oshirish, mahalliy turizmni rivojlantirish hamda “Bir Kamar, Bir Yo’l” mamlakatlarida madaniyatlararo gastronomik tadqiqotlar uchun yangi istiqbollarni taqdim etish maqsadida quyidagi takliflar ishlab chiqildi: Unikal taomlarni yaratish, Restoron tajribasini takomillashtirish, Gastronomik turizm infratuzilmasini yaxshilash, Targ‘ibot strategiyalarini kengaytirish.

Kalit so‘zlar: O‘zbekiston; gastronomik turizm; Xitoy sayyohlari; idrok tahlili; kontent tahlili.

I. Introduction

Since its introduction, the “Belt and Road” initiative has brought brand-new development opportunities to the countries along the route, and has achieved remarkable results in cultural exchanges and tourism cooperation. As an important node of the ancient Silk Road, Uzbekistan, with its unique history, culture and geographical location, has become increasingly close to China in the construction of the “Belt and Road”. In recent years, with the implementation of the policy of mutual visa exemption between China and Uzbekistan, the people-to-people exchanges between the two countries have become more and more frequent, and more and more Chinese tourists have set foot on the land of Uzbekistan to start a journey of discovery. 2023, the number of Chinese tourists going to Uzbekistan exceeded 100,000, and Chinese tourists are exploring the country's history and heritage to its food and culture, which has formed a new phenomenon called “the Silk Road on the tip of the tongue”. This will create a new phenomenon of “Silk Road on the tip of the tongue”.

Cuisine, as an important carrier of culture, occupies a unique place in the tourist experience. The culinary culture of Uzbekistan is a crystallization of the fusion of Eastern and Western civilizations, from the ingredients brought by ancient Cornish traders to today's culinary techniques and food customs that incorporate elements of various cultures, all of which carry rich historical memories and cultural connotations. For example, hand-held rice is not only a local traditional food, but its production and sharing process also contains the imprint of Central Asian nomadic culture and Islamic customs; while the Persian decorations on the Samarkand naan and the unique wrapping process show the charm of cross-cultural fusion, which has become an important factor in attracting Chinese tourists.

However, there is a relative lack of academic research on Uzbekistan's gastronomic tourism, especially a significant gap in perceptual research for the specific group of Chinese tourists, probably due to the late start of tourism exchanges between China and Uzbekistan, which makes it difficult to obtain sufficient and effective data. Past studies have mostly focused on Uzbekistan's architectural heritage, trade history, and other areas, with fewer systematic explorations of perceptions of the gastronomic tourism experience. In the digital age, tourists can conveniently evaluate their tourism experience through online reviews, resulting in a large number of online texts. Online reviews have become an important channel for tourists to express their travel experiences and feelings, and mining these spontaneously generated online texts can provide insights into Chinese tourists' perceptions, emotions, and satisfaction with gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan.

Based on the background of the era of “One Belt, One Road”, this study takes the online reviews of Chinese tourists on Uzbekistan's cuisine in VW Dianping.com as the data source, and applies the method of text content analysis to analyze Chinese tourists' image perception, emotional expression, and satisfaction evaluation of Uzbekistan's cuisine by using the statistical analysis methods such as word frequency analysis, semantic network analysis, and sentiment analysis in the text analysis. Tourism's image perception, emotional expression, satisfaction evaluation and other systematic research. The aim is to reveal the characteristics of Chinese tourists' perceptions of Uzbekistan's gastronomic tourism and analyze the key factors affecting their perceptions. This will not only help Uzbekistan to further optimize its gastronomic tourism products and services and promote the development of the local tourism industry, but also provide new perspectives and empirical evidence for the cross-cultural study of gastronomic tourism in the countries along the “Belt and Road”, and enrich the study of cross-cultural gastronomic tourism.

II. Literature review

Gastronomic tourism has gained significant attention in recent years as a vital component of the broader tourism industry, characterized by the intersection of travel. The literature on this topic reveals various dimensions, including the motivations behind gastronomic tourism, its role in regional identity, and the marketing strategies that can enhance its appeal.

Jalis et. al. conducted an empirical investigation into the perceptions of Western tourists regarding Malaysian gastronomic products, including food, beverages, and food cultures. Their research utilized statistical analyses to assess tourists' preferences and satisfaction levels, highlighting the role of local gastronomy in attracting international visitors. Rojas et. al. explored the motivations and satisfaction levels of gastronomic tourists visiting a prestigious restaurant in Cordoba, Spain. Their research indicated that the reputation of culinary establishments, as highlighted in gastronomic guides, plays a crucial role in shaping tourists' perceptions of local culture and cuisine. This study emphasizes the importance of culinary reputation in attracting

gastronomic tourists. Srivastava conducted an analysis using text mining to explore the culinary experience dimensions of international tourists. By evaluating online reviews from TripAdvisor, the study identified key factors that shape tourists' culinary experiences, emphasizing the role of digital platforms in capturing and disseminating these experiences. This research underscores the importance of understanding tourists' perceptions and preferences, which can inform gastronomic tourism strategies. Carmen Anton Martin et al. examine that iconic food reinforces the effect of perceived value on the intention to repeat the experience, while a generic experience with the local cuisine favours the intention to recommend. Dewi focused on the relationship between culinary diversity, tourism events, and tourist expenditures in Central Lombok, Indonesia. Their findings indicate that a rich culinary landscape, combined with well-managed tourism events, can significantly enhance the destination's image and economic viability. This underscores the importance of integrated destination management strategies that leverage local culinary assets for sustainable tourism development.

From the perspective of gastronomic tourism research, existing studies have paid little attention to tourists' cognition, image perception, and emotional expression regarding gastronomic tourism. In particular, no research has focused on Chinese tourists' cognition, image perception, and emotional expression concerning gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan.

III. Method

In terms of data acquisition, dianping.com was used as the source website for food and travel reviews. Dianping is China's leading local life consumption platform and the earliest independent third-party consumer review website established in the world. Tourists often look for and evaluate the food of tourist destinations through websites such as Dianping, and by counting and analyzing these review data, it is possible to accurately understand tourists' overall evaluation, satisfaction level, and specific suggestions for improvement of local gastronomic tourism. Based on the ratings, number of comments, etc., this paper selects the Top 10 food restaurants in the comprehensive evaluation of Dianping, which are the restaurants that Chinese tourists go to more often and have a strong representation.

Content analysis: content analysis or text analysis is a research method that describes explicit content objectively and quantitatively. Compared with the multivariate analysis method based on questionnaires, the biggest advantage of text analysis is that it can obtain the complete psychological perception of tourists in terms of text analysis. This paper adopts the ROST Content Mining method and the corresponding ROST Content Mining System6.0 software (abbreviation: ROST CM6.0) for the analysis of tourists' perceptions, which is a commonly used analytical tool for online text analysis. It is mainly used for high-frequency word statistics, analysis and visualization of text, and can also be used for sentiment analysis.

Preprocessing: A total of 690 real and valid online reviews were collected about the top 10 restaurants and food in Uzbekistan on the Dianping platform. First of all, a new txt file is created, and the 690 crawled reviews are imported into the file and saved as ANSI encoded and Unicode preserved, which is the original file of Chinese tourists' online evaluation of Uzbekistan's gastronomy and tourism.

Table 1. Top 10 restaurants in Uzbekistan

No.	Restaurant Name
1	Ayvan
2	Syrovarnya(Ташкент)
3	Besh Qozon

4	Shokhrukh Nur
5	Emirhan restaurant
6	Restaurant "KARIMBEK"
7	Samarkand Restaurant
8	Old Bukhara
9	Labi House
10	Chinor

Word frequency analysis : Word frequency analysis is mainly used to count the number of occurrences of words in online text materials and discover the core information hidden in the text content. And with the help of semantic network analysis and other means to discover the regularity in the vocabulary description of the research object. Word frequency analysis is a relatively elementary but very effective text mining method. Through word frequency analysis, this paper finds that there are mainly five types of vocabulary in the tourists' reviews of gastronomic tourism, such as food category, food service, restaurant environment, tourist destination and tourists' perception. The higher frequency of words indicates that a large number of tourists repeatedly mention them, and it also indicates that Uzbekistan's food has left a deep imprint in tourists' brains. By studying the high-frequency words, it is possible to get better information about tourists' perception of food, which is also conducive to the enhancement of gastronomic tourism experience.

Semantic network analysis: The main focus of semantic network analysis is not the words themselves, but the relationship patterns between words. This method can deconstruct the semantic paths between the syntax and concepts of online text content, so as to identify the associations and meanings of the text words, and to realize the deep-level analysis and interpretation of the cognition and brand image perception of gastronomy tourism. In this study, the Net Draw tool in ROST CM 6.0 software is used to construct semantic network diagrams as a way to visualize and analyze the attributes between evaluation objects. To perform semantic network analysis, it is necessary to upload the content of the original txt document of Uzbekistan gastronomic tourism in the parameter settings, and the system will distribute the analysis according to the content of this document. The step-by-step analysis consists of five main steps: extracting high-frequency words, filtering meaningless words, extracting line features, constructing networks and constructing matrices. After a series of operations are completed, the semantic network graph of Chinese tourists' evaluation of Uzbekistan gastronomic tourism is finally formed.

Sentiment analysis: Sentiment analysis is mainly used to identify the type of sentiment of visitors' comments, including positive, neutral, or negative sentiment, by generalizing and reasoning about the emotional color of subjective texts, sentences, or phrases. As a marketing research methodology, sentiment analysis can provide an efficient, real-time response to consumers' overall evaluation of a product or service. For the gastronomic tourism market, a sentiment analysis tool can be used to grasp the overall sentiment level of Chinese tourists towards gastronomic tourism in Uzbekistan. After importing the original evaluation documents and using the default bounding values for sentiment analysis and statistics, the software will estimate the sentiment value of each piece of data from online reviews, and finally assign an overall sentiment value and evaluation.

IV. Findings

(I) Word frequency analysis

Word frequency analysis primarily focuses on tourists' perception of the overall image of gastronomic tourism, and the word frequency analysis uses ROST CM 6.0 software to refine the feature words that appear more frequently in the online comments (text format .txt). The high-frequency words in the top 50 of the sort were mainly summarized so as to identify the overall image of gastronomic tourism. From the top 50 high-frequency words, Chinese tourists' perceptions of Uzbekistan's gastronomic tourism are mainly divided into five categories, including gastronomic products, gastronomic services, gastronomic environment, destinations and tourists' perceptions. The detailed frequency analysis is as follows.

Food Preferences of Chinese Tourists: Frequent mentions of "beef," "lamb," "grilled meats," "roasted lamb," and "steak" highlight their strong preference for local meat dishes, particularly barbecue-style preparations. Terms like "plov" (a traditional rice dish) and "Tashkent" reflect their curiosity toward regional specialties. Additionally, references to "salad," "vegetables," "potatoes," and "pasta" indicate a balanced dietary focus, emphasizing both staple foods and side dishes to ensure meal diversity.

Restaurant Experience: This dimension encompasses both service and ambiance. High-frequency terms such as "restaurant," "delicious," "flavor," "taste," and "texture" indicate that tourists prioritize the taste and palatability of dishes, with "deliciousness" serving as a critical evaluation criterion. Mentions of "ambiance," "service," and "waitstaff" highlight tourists' expectations for restaurant environments and service quality, as these elements directly impact the overall experience. The occasional reference to "service charge" may reflect attention to additional fees. The high frequency of "price-performance ratio" underscores tourists' emphasis on value-for-money assessments. Notably, terms like "English" (116 mentions) and "menu" (75 mentions) reveal a latent demand for English-language menus or services, emphasizing the importance of accessibility for non-local language speakers.

Tourist Behavior: Seeking Local Authenticity. The frequent use of terms like "local characteristics," "local," "location," "Uzbekistan," and "Bukhara" reflects tourists' expectations for restaurants to embody regional distinctiveness and cultural ambiance. Visitors desire to experience local customs and traditions while dining, blending culinary exploration with cultural immersion. The prominence of "check-in behavior" highlights tourists' inclination to share visits to popular destinations on social media. Additionally, the high frequency of "internet-famous" underscores the influence of social media influencers and viral restaurant recommendations on tourists' dining choices, indicating that online trends significantly shape their decision-making processes.

To summarize, Chinese tourists' evaluations of Uzbek restaurants focus on three core aspects—food quality, dining environment and service quality, and local cultural characteristics—while also emphasizing value for money and the influence of social media recommendations. Signature restaurants in cities like Samarkand and Bukhara, as well as eateries near landmarks such as Registan Square, are more likely to become popular check-in destinations. Enhancing the availability of English-language services (e.g., menus, staff assistance) would further improve the overall tourist experience, particularly for non-local visitors seeking convenience and cultural immersion.

Table 2. High-frequency words of perceived images of gastronomic tourism

No.	Keywords.	word frequency	No.	Keywords.	word frequency
1	Restaurant	366	26	Evening	63
2	Delicious	323	27	Steak	63

3	Flavor	271	28	Stan	60
4	Ambience	262	29	Roast Lamb	57
5	Beef	211	30	Hit the road	55
6	Salad	204	31	Specialty	54
7	Service	203	32	Eating	51
8	Mutton	182	33	Platters	51
9	Plov	165	34	Hotel	49
10	Grilled Meat	142	35	Soup	47
11	Vegetables	129	36	Potato	47
12	Server	129	37	internet- famous	47
13	Taste	127	38	Places	46
14	English	116	39	Tashkent	44
15	Samarkand	101	40	Super	44
16	Bukhara	100	41	Pasta	43
17	Uzbekistan	100	42	Tourist	42
18	Somsa	98	43	Cheap	42
19	Location	94	44	Cream	42
20	Local	88	45	Come here	42
21	Cuisine	88	46	Overall	42
22	Value for Money	81	47	Suitable	41
23	Service Charge	80	48	Taste	40
24	Menu	75	49	Side	39
25	Registan Square	73	50	Tomato	39

(II) Semantic network analysis

Although word frequency analysis can reflect the main features of things by extracting the attributes of phrases, it cannot reflect the connection of phrases in specific meanings as well as the deep structural relationship of the text. Semantic network analysis, on the other hand, can visualize the relationship between elements by constructing a network diagram of conceptual and semantic relationships. In the semantic network analysis, firstly, the original text of the review is subjected to lexical processing. Then, after extracting high-frequency words and filtering some meaningless words, VNA files are further generated by feature analysis. Finally, the VNA file is imported into Net Draw software to finally generate a semantic network diagram of Chinese tourists' perception of Uzbekistan gastronomic tourism. From the perspective of hierarchical structure, the semantic network graph shows the characteristics of “core-edge”, the closer the distance of the words from the center node (core node), the closer the connection with the center node words and the sparseness of the lines represents the frequency of co-occurrence, and the denser the lines, the more frequent the co-occurrence.

Overall, the semantic network graph shows a “core-edge” structure, which can be divided into four layers.

The first layer is the core layer, which directly linked to the central node "restaurant," this layer comprises keywords such as "beef," "lamb," "grilled meat," "salad," and "vegetables," , highlighting tourists' primary focus on food variety. Additional core terms like "flavor,"

"taste," and "delicious" emphasize the centrality of culinary quality in shaping their perceptions. These elements collectively form the foundational image of Uzbek gastronomic tourism.

The second layer is the Sub-Core Layer. Expanding on the core themes, this layer includes "ambiance," "service," "waitstaff," and "service charge," underscoring tourists' attention to environmental aesthetics, service professionalism, and cost transparency.

The third layer is Transitional Layer. Keywords such as "location," "local," "affordability," "unique characteristics," and "English" reveal secondary priorities, including expectations for culturally immersive experiences and geographical accessibility.

The fourth layer is Edge Layer: Words like "hotel" and "square" (e.g., Registan Square) occupy the outermost tier, representing tangential associations with broader travel infrastructure and landmark proximity.

This hierarchical structure—core → sub-core → transitional → edge—visually maps the multidimensional cognitive framework through which Chinese tourists evaluate Uzbek gastronomic tourism.

Fig. 1 Semantic network of the gastronomic tourism

(III) Sentiment Analysis of Textual Reviews

Textual reviews have invisible features and need to be further analyzed by sentiment analysis in content analysis to capture tourists' feelings, which belongs to the overall perceptual evaluation. The sentiment function of ROST software was used to analyze the perceived emotions of Chinese tourists towards Uzbekistan gastronomic tourism (Table 3).

The results reveal a predominance of positive sentiments (86.96%), with negative sentiments accounting for 10.14%. High-frequency positive keywords such as "delicious" dominate the dataset, indicating strong approval and satisfaction with Uzbek cuisine. For example, comments like "The food is exceptionally flavorful" reflect tourists' enjoyment of local dishes. In terms of negative words, the comments include "The food is a bit greasy and has a heavy taste." Comments such as "the baked buns were not delicious" imply that some Chinese tourists were dissatisfied with their gastronomic tourism experience in Uzbekistan.

Table 3. Sentiment analysis for gastronomic tourism

Type of emotion	Percentage/%
Positive sentiment	86.96%
Neutral sentiment	2.90%
Negative sentiment	10.14%

There are two main reasons for the dominance of positive emotions. The first one is the attraction of gastronomic characteristics. Uzbek cuisine has a unique flavor, such as hand-held rice and barbecue meat, etc. The rich use of spices and the unique way of cooking may bring Chinese tourists a fresh and wonderful taste sensation, and satisfy the tourists' desire and curiosity of exploring the exotic cuisines. The second cultural experience fusion, tasting food is often accompanied by an in-depth understanding of the local food culture, traditional customs, tourists enjoy the food at the same time, experience a unique cultural atmosphere, this cultural fusion of experience increases the added value of gastronomic tourism, enhance the tourists' goodwill.

Negative sentiment exists because, first, discomfort with dietary differences, despite the characteristics of Uzbek cuisine, there are differences in the food culture of the two countries, and some Chinese tourists may not be accustomed to the taste of the local food and the combination of ingredients, such as the special taste of some Central Asian specialty dairy products, the cooking doneness of certain meats, and the lack of vegetables. Secondly, the service is poor. In the process of dining in restaurants, there are problems such as low service efficiency, communication barriers (language barrier, etc.), and unsatisfactory dining environment, which affect tourists' overall evaluation of gastronomic tourism.

V. Suggestions

Combining the main results of the study, the following suggestions are made:

(I) Create culinary specialties. Highlighting signature dishes, centering on high-frequency specialty foods such as “plov”, “barbecue meat”, “lamb”, “beef” and so on, while exploring their historical origins and cultural significance to build a cultural IP. For example, host a Plov Festival to showcase regional variations of the dish, inviting visitors to participate in cooking and tasting experiences. Innovate in menu development by preserving traditional flavors while integrating international trends and health-conscious concepts. Examples include creating low-salt or low-sugar versions of classic dishes, or introducing fusion cuisine that blends local ingredients with Western culinary techniques. Create an "Uzbekistan Food Map" that highlights iconic restaurants and dishes in cities like Samarkand, Bukhara, and Tashkent (e.g., plov, roasted lamb, and dining spots around Registan Square), forming regional culinary brands.

(II) Optimize the restaurant experience. First, enhance the environmental atmosphere. The food experience is not only a taste feast, but also a multi-sensory depth of participation in the process. Based on the “environment” high-frequency demand, create a restaurant environment with both local cultural characteristics and a sense of comfort, such as the use of local cultural elements, the integration of cultural stories, Islamic culture, Silk Road elements, etc., to create a special restaurant decoration style. Create an immersive dining environment to enhance the sensory stimulation and emotional connection of travelers, thus deepening their understanding and recognition of the destination culture. Second, strengthen service training, for “service” “waiter” high-frequency words, strengthen restaurant staff training, restaurant waiters to carry out service etiquette, foreign language (especially English) communication training, etc., to enhance the level of service and professionalism, and timely response to tourists' needs. Third, reasonable pricing

charges, comprehensive cost and tourists' psychological expectations of pricing, clear service fees and other charges, improve the cost-effective, provide different price packages to meet the diversified needs of tourists to enhance the sense of trust.

(III) Improvement of supporting services for gastronomic tourism. First of all, optimize the location of restaurants, because in unfamiliar tourist environments, tourists are highly dependent on clear guidelines and convenient transportation. Therefore, restaurants can be reasonably distributed in popular scenic spots, transportation hubs and hotel gathering areas to facilitate tourists' access. Meanwhile, the construction of transportation network, improvement of signage system, parking, etc. can be strengthened to reduce travel barriers for tourists and improve convenience. Second, provide language support and create multilingual (especially English and Chinese) menus with food pictures to facilitate tourists' ordering. Thirdly, develop gastronomic tourism routes, linking specialty restaurants and food markets in Samarkand and Bukhara, and launching one-day or multi-day gastronomic tourism routes in combination with local cultural attractions.

(IV) Expand Promotional Strategies. First, leverage influencer marketing to create viral dining spots. In the digital age, social media platforms offer powerful channels for culinary promotion. Operators should prioritize building a strong online presence and reputation. Collaborate with renowned travel bloggers and food influencers to showcase featured restaurants through engaging content like "A Day of Uzbek Cuisine" videos or photo guides. Encourage tourists to share geotagged check-in posts on social media by offering incentives. Establish an official hashtag (e.g., #Taste Of Uzbekistan) to curate reviews and recommendations. Second, diversify marketing channels. Promote dishes through tourism exhibitions, social media, and travel websites by sharing high-quality food photography, videos, and customer testimonials to attract potential visitors. Third, organize culinary festivals and events. Aligning with high-frequency terms like "evening," launch nighttime food markets or illuminated culinary festivals. Host themed food events during holidays to draw crowds and enhance the cultural appeal of Uzbek cuisine.

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